

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN_MSCA_TIME2EMERGE: V1.0 – 31.05.2026

Project number:	101205676
Project acronym:	TIME2EMERGE
Project name:	Assessing the optimal strategic and sustainable investment timing in emerging technologies: a prospective techno-sustainability assessment
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History of changes			
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1.0	28.05.2026	Initial version	Maxim Tschulkow

Abstract

European society must urgently transition from fossil dependency to a self-sustained economy, with emerging sustainable technologies as a key foundation. However, many of these technologies are still in development, making investment timing uncertain. Current sustainability assessments treat emerging technologies as if they are ready for commercialization, despite their future implementation. This misalignment leads to uncertain and potentially inaccurate sustainability evaluations, risking misguided investments. Given the urgency of this transition, society has neither the time nor the resources to afford such failures. Hence, within my project TIME2EMERGE, I will develop an innovative techno-sustainability assessment framework to prospectively evaluate the strategic sustainable investment timing in emerging technologies that will be defined by the expected future technological readiness, economic feasibility, and environmental soundness at the commercialisation point of time. This approach will initiate a paradigm shift moving away from a present-based "What is the sustainability of the emerging technology?" towards a future-based approach "When is sustainability achieved?" My expertise in prospective sustainability assessment, Prof. Tony Kiss's specialization in dynamic process systems engineering, and access to the emerging technology electrochemical CO₂ reduction at TU-Delft will support the development of this innovative framework. This project will drive a crucial shift toward prospective techno-sustainability, enhancing the precision and predictability of evaluations across disciplines. It will prevent false investments and guide R&D efforts, accelerating the development of technologies that reduce environmental impact while fostering sustainable economic growth and job creation. Additionally, the project will deepen my expertise, positioning me as a key link between academia and industry, and strengthening my path toward an independent academic career.

1. Introduction and purpose

The purpose of this data management plan (DMP) is to provide a detailed description of the procedures and protocols for managing the datasets generated throughout the lifetime of the MSCA project TIME2EMERGE. This plan outlines the main data management principles, including data standards and metadata, sharing, archiving, preservation, and security. This is a living document that will be regularly updated during the project. It will be stored in the Zenodo repository under the name TIME2EMERGE_01_DMP_V1.0_WP4.pdf.

2. Data Summary

2.1 Re-use of existing data and models

The project will re-use several existing models and datasets as inputs for the TIME2EMERGE techno-sustainability framework. Foreground data generated within the project will be distinguished from third-party data, for which licences restrict re-distribution.

2.2 Models (re-used, not redistributed)

Economic model: A real options analysis approach will be re-used to define the optimal economic timing of investments under market uncertainty. Only project-specific parameterisations and code developed in the project will be shared openly; underlying copyrighted material (e.g. full texts, proprietary datasets) will not be redistributed.

Environmental model: A consequential life cycle assessment (LCA) approach will be applied to reflect decision-consequential impacts and prospective marginal technologies. Background life cycle inventories will be based on EcoInvent and IMAGE scenarios via the Premise workflow; these licensed databases will not be made openly available, but scripts, scenarios, and aggregated results will be shared.

Technological model: Aspen Plus models of the ECO₂R technology will be developed and calibrated. Native Aspen files will be shared only where licences permit and after removing confidential industrial information; key model structures and results will be exported to open formats (e.g. CSV, diagrams, documentation) for public re-use.

2.3 Data (re-used, not redistributed when restricted)

Economic data: Licensed and/or commercial sources (e.g. Statista, IEA) and open literature will be used as inputs. Only derived indicators, aggregated tables, and parameter values will be shared, not the original proprietary datasets.

Environmental data: Ecoinvent and IMAGE scenario data will be used under existing licences. Publicly shared outputs will consist of derived inventories, impact results, and scenario definitions, ensuring no redistribution of licence-protected content.

Technological data: Foreground life cycle inventory data from technology developers (via the e-Refinery platform at TU Delft) may include confidential information. Raw confidential data will remain on secure TU Delft servers; anonymised/aggregated datasets and modelling assumptions will be shared when compatible with IPR and contractual constraints.

Re-use of existing data and models has been chosen to: 1) build on established, peer-reviewed

methods, 2) ensure comparability with other studies, and 3) reduce duplication of data collection efforts. Alternative data sources or models will be considered only where licence terms or methodological constraints prevent their use.

2.4 Newly generated models and data

The project will generate a new interdisciplinary framework for prospective techno-sustainability assessment with time as a common scale for investment and sustainability timing.

Foreground outputs (to be shared, subject to justified restrictions):

- Framework specification: Conceptual and mathematical description of the TIME2EMERGE framework (documentation, diagrams, pseudo-code).

- Model implementations:

- *Economic*: Real options implementation in Python and/or Excel, plus input parameter sets.
- *Environmental*: Brightway/Activity Browser projects, Premise workflows, foreground life cycle inventory datasets, and scenario files.
- *Technological*: Aspen Plus models and associated scaling/operating assumptions, with open surrogates or exports where proprietary formats cannot be shared fully.

- Prospective datasets: Time-dependent techno-economic and environmental data points/sets for the selected emerging technology, including scenarios and uncertainty descriptors.

2.5 Types and formats

TIME2EMERGE aims to develop a next-generation techno-sustainability framework to assess the most optimal, strategic and sustainable timing of investment for emerging technologies, using electrochemical CO₂ reduction as a case study technology. The project will generate data using a combination of quantitative methods ranging from already in use methodologies (WP1) to develop a novel interdisciplinary concept, existing methodologies to validate the data (WP2), to finally apply both, WP1 and WP2, to a case study technology, electrochemical reduction of CO₂ (WP3).

TIME2EMERGE will generate data in various formats that will be accessible using free software.

These formats are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Types of data and formats

Type of data	Description	Format
Compressed data	Compression will be used for packaging files with similar and/or complementary content	.rar
Data bases and notes	Data (bases) produced from research by the researcher. Novel modified EcoInvent databases will be generated.	.odt, .doc, .xlsx, .pdf, ecoSpold2 formats
Codes and data	Storing and sharing data that are imported, processed and/or created in a Python, R environment (IMAGE), and Aspen Plus.	py, .ipynb, .rdm, .rda, Rdata, Aspen formats
Images	Images produced for scientific and dissemination purposes	.jpg, .png
Videos	Videos produced for scientific and dissemination purposes.	.mp4
Reports	Scientific, technical, and dissemination purposes	.pdf
Presentations	Scientific and dissemination purposes.	.pdf, .ppt

Paper pre-prints	Green open access according to the HorizonEurope guidelines	.pdf
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Types and formats will remain in as indicated in the DMP (docx, pdf, xlsx, py, ipynb, ecoSpold2, R files, Aspen formats). In addition to that, all key results will also be exported in interoperable, open formats (CSV/TSV, JSON, or similar) with clear units and variable definitions.

2.6 Purpose and link to objectives

The reuse and generation of data is linked to the objectives of TIME2EMERGE with the purpose to:

- generate and share high-quality, well-documented datasets and models that support the development and testing of the TIME2EMERGE conceptualized framework in WP1, and the data validation supported by reused and newly developed methods and models in WP2,
- inform strategic investment decisions in emerging technologies, specifically focusing on electrochemical CO₂ reduction technology, by providing transparent, re-usable techno-economic and environmental evidence (WP3),
- enable combination of TIME2EMERGE outputs with other datasets and models (e.g. energy systems, policy scenarios) through interoperable formats and rich metadata,
- and support educational and training activities by providing curated examples of emerging technology assessments.

2.7 Size and provenance

TIME2EMERGE will create and utilize data from various sources, including literature, books, websites, secondary data from different public databases (e.g., Statista, IEA), and communication materials (videos, preprints, presentations, journal articles, and reports). Third-party data, for which licences restrict re-distribution, will be treated confidential. In Table 2, a tentative summary of the different types of datasets that will be generated by TIME2EMERGE, linked to the six work packages (WP) of the project. The total estimated amount of data is approximately 9.2 GB, with individual datasets ranging from 10 MB to 3,000 MB.

Table 2: Description of datasets. (TH) represents third-party licensed data that is bound to confidentiality/restricted of sharing and (PG) are project-generated (foreground) data allowing for open-access.

	Description of dataset	Type	Format	Size
WP1	Development of cutting-edge next-generation sustainability assessment			
	Real options analysis	Excel/python	.xlsx, .ipynb, .py,	< 20 MB
	Consequential LCA	Excel/python	.xlsx, .ipynb, .py,	< 10 MB
TH	Ex-Ante process system engineering, Aspen Plus	Aspen Plus	Aspen formats	< 20 MB
PG	Development of next-generation techno-sustainability framework	Excel/python	.xlsx, .py, .ipynb, .pdf	< 50-100 MB
WP2	Acquisition and validation of prospective data			
PG	Technical data of ECO ₂ R technology (ies)	Aspen Plus	Aspen formats	< 60- 200MB
PG	Technical data of benchmark technologies (multiple)	Aspen Plus	Aspen formats	< 60-200 MB
PG	Environmental data: foreground data of ECO ₂ R	Excel/python	.xlsx, .ipynb, .py	< 10 MB
PG	Environmental data: foreground data of benchmark	Excel/python	.xlsx, .ipynb, .py	< 10 MB
TH	Environmental data: Background Ecoinvent database for ECO ₂ R and benchmark technologies	Ecoinvent database	ecoSpold2 formats	< 2 GB
PG	Environmental data: newly generated background Ecoinvent database for ECO ₂ R and benchmark technologies, using IMAGE.	Ecoinvent database	ecoSpold2 formats	< 2 GB
TH	IMAGE	R data	.rdm, .rda	< 200 MB
PG	Economic data for ECO ₂ R technology	Excel/python	.xlsx, .ipynb, .py	< 50 MB
PG	Economic data for benchmark technologies	Excel/python	.xlsx, .ipynb, .py	< 50 MB
WP3	Application of the validated cutting-edge sustainability framework on ECO₂R			
PG	Results and outcomes	Report	.pdf	< 10 MB
WP4	Management			
PG	T4.1-3: Coordinating scientific quality assurance, Scientific and administrative risk management, project administration,	Report	.pdf, .dox, .xlsx	< 50 MB
PG	T4.4: Data management plan	Report	.pdf	< 20 MB
PG	D4: Reporting of the progress to EC (M12 and 24)	Report	.pdf	< 40 MB
WP5	Training and knowledge exchange			
TH	T5.1: Aspen Plus & electrochemical courses	Files, lectures	Aspen plus formats, .pdf	< 50 MB
TH	T5.2: Acquire technical insights of IMAGE	Files, lectures	.rdm, .rda, .Rdata, .pdf	< 200 MB
PG	T5.3: Continuous & iterative knowledge exchange between researchers, supervisor, and host institution	Report	.docx, .pdf	< 10 MB
PG	Career Development plan	Report	.pdf	< 20 MB
WP6	Dissemination, exploitation, and communication (DEC)			
PG	Dissemination and communication plan	Report	.pdf	< 20 MB
PG	Final preprint versions of papers for expert audiences (Estimation: 3 preprints)	Paper preprint	.pdf	< 20 MB
PG	Press articles	Publication	.pdf	< 20 MB
PG	Infographics of the published articles	Image	.jpg, .png	< 200 MB
PG	Report on social media (LinkedIn, etc.)	Report	.pdf	< 20 MB
PG	Presentations at international conferences	Presentations	.rar	< 200 MB
PG	Presentations at events for non-expert audiences	Presentations	.rar	< 200 MB
PG	Further funding proposals/applications	Report	.pdf	< 20 MB
PG	Open-access booklet	Booklet	.pdf	< 200 MB
PG	Briefing report	Report	.pdf	< 20 MB
PG	Pictures/videos of the MSCA project and its outcomes	Image/Video	.jpg, .png, .mp4	< 3 GB

2. 8 Data utility

The data generated by TIME2EMERGE will be relevant for various stakeholders, including scholars, academic, industry, policymakers, and decision-makers, involved in strategic and sustainable development and investment in emerging and sustainable technologies but also creating strategies for incentive policies. The outcomes of this two-year project will serve both as a precedent and a toolkit for assessing novel emerging and sustainable technologies, accelerating R&D, and allocating financial resources and time in the most efficient way.

3. FAIR data

TIME2EMERGE is fully committed to the FAIR principles. In this regard, several actions are planned aimed at maximizing the **findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reproducibility** of the data and results that I will generate during the project

3.1 Making data findable

All openly shared datasets, code, and documentation will be deposited in Zenodo under the [TIME2EMERGE Community](#) and automatically indexed in the OpenAIRE Research Graph via the CORDIS grant information, linked to the following CORDIS ID (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101205676>) and DOI (<https://doi.org/10.3030/101205676>).

Each deposition will receive a DOI and will include following information to ensure unambiguous identification:

- Project identifiers: Grant agreement number (101205676), and CORDIS ID,
- Creator identifiers: ORCID for all contributing researchers;
- Funding information: "Horizon Europe - MSCA TIME2EMERGE, GA 101205676".

Additionally, data files will be assigned intuitive dataset identifiers, created according to the convention outlined in Table 3.

Table 3: Convention for creating the dataset identifier.

Components	Example
Project name	TIME2EMERGE (always)
Title of the dataset	Presentation_MSCA_Project
Version of the dataset (Zenodo will allow to keep several versions)	V1.0
Work Package associated to the dataset	WP6
Format of the dataset	ppt
Example dataset file identifier: TIME2EMERGE_Presentation_MSCA_Project_V1.0_WP6.ppt	

Rich, searchable metadata will be provided following the DataCite schema plus community-specific fields (e.g. technology name, TRL, scenario year, functional unit, impact categories).

Keywords will include: "sustainable and strategic investment timing", "prospective techno-sustainability assessment", "emerging technologies", "real options analysis", "consequential life cycle assessment", "process systems engineering", plus technology-specific terms (e.g. "CO₂ electroreduction").

Archived data will be accompanied by detailed metadata (in text or PDF format), which will be updated as necessary and will include the information outlined in Table 4. It will ensure that metadata

is publicly and openly accessible. To compile the metadata, I will use search keywords to facilitate cross-referencing information across different data files.

Table 4: Contents of a generic metadata file associated to a given dataset.

Components	Description
Dataset Identifier	The ID will result from the naming convention provided in the previous table
Title of the Dataset	The title of the dataset, which will be easily searchable and findable
Work Package	MSCA project work package
Dataset dissemination	Where will the dataset be disseminated (e.g. peer reviewed journal)
Type Format	See table with formats in Data Summary section
Expected Size	Dataset size (see size in the Data Summary section)
Source	How was the dataset generated (e.g. <i>simulation</i>)
Repository	Zenodo
DOI (if known)	The DOI will be entered once the dataset has been deposited
Date of Submission	The date of submission will be added once the dataset has been uploaded on the repository
Keywords	Keywords associated with the dataset
Version Number	Version number to keep track of changes

Metadata will be harvestable and indexable through Zenodo's OAI-PMH endpoint and OpenAIRE's harvesting mechanisms, ensuring broad discoverability. In case of content of the metadata modification, creation date will be updated accordingly ensuring metadata are versioned and kept current.

3.2 Making data accessible

Repositories: Zenodo (including the [TIME2EMERGE Community](#) and, where applicable, the EU Open Research Repository collections) will be the primary repository for open data, code, and documentation. TU Delft institutional storage will host working copies and any restricted datasets.

All Zenodo records will receive a DOI, and DOIs will resolve to landing pages with downloadable files and full metadata.

Open vs. restricted datasets:

- Open datasets: All foreground datasets and code that do not contain confidential or third-party licensed material will be made openly available as soon as possible, and at the latest by the end of the project or after any justified embargo.

- Restricted datasets:

* Confidential industrial data from technology developers (e.g. detailed process parameters, proprietary configurations).

* Third-party licensed data (e.g. raw Ecolnvent, Statista, IEA data, Aspen libraries).

These will not be shared openly. Instead, the DMP will provide descriptions and, where possible, anonymised/aggregated derivatives.

Embargoes: Where necessary to protect IPR (e.g. patent applications) or to allow publication, an embargo of up to 12 months may be applied to certain datasets and code. The embargo duration, justification, and planned release date will be specified in the Zenodo record at the time of deposition.

During the embargo, metadata will remain openly accessible, and interested users may request access under appropriate agreements (e.g. NDAs), handled on a case-by-case basis by the beneficiary.

Access procedures for restricted data:

For restricted or sensitive data, requests will be handled by the PI (or designated Data Manager at TU Delft). Requesters will contact a dedicated email address provided in the metadata; requests and decisions will be logged. Access may be granted under specific conditions (e.g. data-sharing agreements, NDAs) to protect IPR and third-party rights.

Metadata: Metadata will remain openly available under CC0 even if underlying data must be withdrawn or are no longer accessible. They will include clear information on how to obtain access, where applicable.

3.3 Making data interoperable

The project will follow the DataCite metadata schema and FAIR principles and will apply community standards where available. For LCA data, formats and naming will be aligned with the ecoSpold2/ILCD conventions used in EcoInvent and Brightway; for economic and technological data, variables and units will be documented in codebooks and READMEs.

Key numerical results will be provided in open, machine-readable formats (CSV/TSV, JSON) with explicit unit declarations, coordinate systems (for time/horizon), and controlled vocabularies for main entities (technology, scenario, impact category).

Where project-specific vocabularies or ontologies are needed (e.g. for scenario naming), these will be documented and, where possible, mapped to existing ontologies or classification systems (e.g. IPCC scenario naming, Eurostat energy classifications). The vocabularies and mapping tables will be shared as open resources in Zenodo.

3.4 Increasing data re-use

For each dataset or code repository, a detailed README will describe: study purpose, methodology, variable definitions, units, data cleaning steps, version, and links to related publications and datasets. Where appropriate, codebooks and workflow diagrams (for Brightway, Premise, Aspen, Python/R scripts) will be provided to document data processing pipelines.

Typical re-use cases include:

- Re-analysis of techno-economic and environmental performance of ECO₂R and similar technologies;
- Integration of TIME2EMERGE outputs into energy systems or policy models;
- Methodological benchmarking for prospective LCA and real options analysis in emerging technologies.

Data will be licensed using a standard, Horizon Europe-compliant licence:

- Research data: CC BY 4.0 (or CC0 where appropriate);

- Software/code: a permissive open-source licence (e.g. MIT or BSD-3-Clause), to be specified in each code repository;

- Metadata: CC0.

Where a more restrictive licence is necessary (e.g. due to third-party constraints), this will be clearly justified in the DMP and in the metadata.

Data provenance will be documented through version control (e.g. Git), explicit references to source datasets (DOIs, database versions), and changelogs describing major modifications. Quality assurance will include internal peer review of key datasets, automated checks (e.g. unit and consistency checks), and verification against model expectations (e.g. mass/energy balance).

4. Other research outputs

For non-data digital outputs (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models), the same FAIR principles will apply: assignment of DOIs via Zenodo, rich metadata, open formats where possible, and clear licensing (e.g. MIT/BSD for code).

Physical outputs are not expected to be central to this project; if generated (e.g. lab samples), their management will follow TU Delft and partner institutional policies. Any such outputs relevant for re-use will be documented in the updated versions of the DMP.

5. Allocation of resources

Personnel time for data management (curation, documentation, QA, and deposition) is the main cost and will be covered by the TIME2EMERGE budget under management and indirect costs. TU Delft provides institutional storage and backup infrastructure; Zenodo and OpenAIRE are free-of-charge repositories for Horizon Europe projects.

The PI (or named Data Manager) will coordinate data management across WPs, supported by WP leads who are responsible for preparing and documenting their respective datasets. The DMP will be reviewed and updated at least once per year and at key project milestones.

Long-term preservation will be ensured primarily through Zenodo (minimum 20-year retention) and TU Delft institutional repositories. Decisions on what to preserve long-term will consider scientific value, legal constraints, and storage costs and will be documented in the final DMP update.

6. Data security

While most open data do not require strong confidentiality measures, the project will still implement appropriate security and integrity practices: version-controlled repositories, regular backups, and checksums for archived datasets.

Confidential or restricted data from industrial partners will be stored on secure TU Delft servers with access control (role-based permissions), encrypted transfers where needed, and separation from open datasets used for publication.

7. Ethics

For the project, no ethical, security, and AI issues are applicable to the research presented here. Gender and diversity issues do not apply to the project as it will develop a novel method for technology evaluation to be used independently of sex and gender. However, gender and diversity aspects will be considered in the outreach activities, and scientific collaborations.

The project does not process personal data and is not expected to involve direct human or animal subjects. Nevertheless, it engages with technologies that have environmental and societal implications. The DMP will therefore include reflection on responsible research and innovation aspects, such as potential distributional impacts of technology deployment and consideration of gender and diversity in outreach and training activities.

No informed consent procedures are needed for data sharing, as no personal data are collected. Any future changes to this assumption (e.g. stakeholder surveys) would trigger an ethics amendment and DMP update to include consent and anonymisation procedures.

8. Other issues

Currently, the project does not utilize any other national, funder, sectorial, or departmental procedures for data management.